

Inverse Cantorian Infinity

Jonathan Sadowsky
jonathan.sadowsky.3000@gmail.com

Abstract This paper develops a formal transformation between non-causal and causal representations of infinite structures and demonstrates that Cantorian Infinity, when expressed in the causal domain, exhibits a circular dependency among its core properties. Building on this analysis, a mathematically coherent but mutually incompatible inverse framework is constructed, not philosophical, grounded in relative cardinality and nominalism. The work aims to clarify foundational assumptions underlying infinite processes and provide a systematic causal interpretation of classical paradoxes such as Galileo's.

1. Introduction

1.1. The Destination Before the Journey

This paper covers a large mesh of interconnected topics. The path through these topics was carefully chosen. However, due to the linear nature of this paper, a single reading may not be sufficient to internalize a full understanding of the ideas in this paper. As such, I feel that it will greatly help to understand the destination if the path of the journey is known from the start.

The first main topic of discussion will take place in section 2. A transformation will be shown to exist between the non-causal domain representation of Cantorian Infinity and a causal domain representation. I will show that the causal domain is not just a model for Non-Causal Cantorian Infinity, but that the non-causal and causal domains are fully interchangeable. This is similar to the time and frequency domain transformations of the Fourier transform. With regards to Fourier transforms, some problems are easier to solve in one domain, and looking at a problem in both domains provides insights that are not easily discernable when only viewing a single domain. Three properties are required for Cantorian Infinity to exist in the causal domain. The most surprising part of this analysis is that the causal properties form a circular dependency structure (Figure 1, Causal Cantorian Infinity). Within the scope of this dependency structure, the properties of Causal Cantorian Infinity are self-consistent. Once the circular dependency structure is identified, it will be easy to identify the equivalent circular dependency structure in the non-causal version of Cantorian Infinity.

Causal Cantorian Infinity

Causal Inverse Cantorian Infinity

Figure 1: Generic Visualization of the Causal Dependency Structure

The second main topic of discussion will take place in section 3. With the understanding of a circular dependency structure in Causal Cantorian Infinity, I will investigate whether there are other ways that the core properties can be constrained. Changing any one property will break their self-consistency. But what if all properties were changed? Algorithmic concepts borrowed from computer science [1] will be used to show that the new constraints for the core properties are also both valid and self-consistent. It will be shown that these alternate property constraints are “inverse” values of the property constraints of Causal Cantorian Infinity and contain an equivalent circular dependency structure (Figure 1, Causal Inverse Cantorian Infinity).

The third main topic of discussion will then take place in section 4. The analysis of the inverse framework in section 3 is completely in the causal domain. I will introduce the mathematical tool to show the causal and non-causal domains of the inverse framework are also fully interchangeable.

The fourth main topic of discussion will take place in sections 5 and 6. I will work through several classical math problems using both frameworks of infinity in the causal domain to show whether their results are compatible or not. Critically, the properties of Cantorian Infinity and the inverse framework are mutually exclusive. Because they are “inverses” of each other, only one set of properties can be true. They define two independent mathematical universes. Since both property sets contain a circular dependency structure, the most that can be claimed is that they are self-consistent.

The ideas of the inverse framework are a distinct alternative to the established framework of Cantorian Infinity. Cantorian Infinity has been explored, studied, and taught by multiple generations of mathematicians. The non-causal ideas of Cantorian Infinity are ingrained in our minds, but these thought processes may hinder our understanding of the causal domain and the inverse framework. As such, I encourage you to set aside long-held ideas and mentally engage with an alternate and completely foreign perspective that will challenge your deeply held beliefs about the behaviors of infinity.

1.1. Definitions

Table 1 provides a list of relevant definitions for common terms used throughout this document. Formal axiomatic definitions are provided in section 7.

Table 1: Definitions

Term	Definition
Causality	The relationship between cause and effect. In this document, specifically referring to the temporal steps of an algorithmic process. For example, first step 1, then step 2, and so on.
Non-Causal Domain	An interpretation of mathematics where relationships exist without process. For example, the function $f(x) = x-1$ has no process but rather defines a relationship between a set of ordered pairs $(x, f(x))$.
Causal Domain	An interpretation of mathematics where relationships exist as processes. For example, the function $f(x) = x-1$ is a process that converts x into $f(x)$ through a series of steps.
Finite-Event Causality	An interpretation of the causal domain where processes must complete in a finite number of steps.

Infinite-Event Causality	An interpretation of the causal domain where processes can only be completed using an infinite number of steps.
Cardinality	The number of elements in a set
Equal Cardinality	If a one-to-one mapping exists between two sets, whether finite or infinite, the number of elements in the two sets are equal.
Relative Cardinality	If a one-to-one mapping exists between two infinite sets, the number of elements in the two sets are not necessarily equal. Relative comparisons can be made between the number of elements in each set.
Philosophy of Universals	Whether mathematical concepts exist as real abstract objects or not.
Reification	An interpretation of the Philosophy of Universals where mathematical concepts are real abstract objects.
Nominalism (Anti-Reification)	An interpretation of the Philosophy of Universals where mathematical concepts are not real abstract objects.
State Mapping Property	A causal domain property concerning whether the mapping between states (causal steps) is considered reified or nominalist.
Property of Shiftability	A property of the causal domain describing the resultant behavior of an insert or removal operation on an infinite list.
Seamless Shift	An interpretation of the Property of Shiftability where an insert operation on an infinite list can complete seamlessly. That is, all elements are shifted and the new element is seamlessly inserted into the list.
Deadlock	An interpretation of the Property of Shiftability where an insert operation on an infinite list cannot be completed because the list cannot shift.
Cantorian Infinity	The framework of infinity developed by Cantor, eventually formalized as the ZFC axiomatic system of infinity.
Inverse Cantorian Infinity	For want of a better name, a new framework of infinity constructed in this paper which is mutually exclusive with Cantorian Infinity. Also commonly referred to in this paper as simply “the inverse framework”.
Non-Causal Cantorian Infinity	The non-causal interpretation of Cantorian Infinity as commonly understood in mathematics, existing without process.
Causal Cantorian Infinity	The causal domain interpretation of Cantorian Infinity.
Non-Causal Inverse Cantorian Infinity	The non-causal interpretation of the inverse framework.
Causal Inverse Cantorian Infinity	The causal interpretation of the inverse framework.
Element	A single object that is a member of a set, list, series, or sequence.
Set	In this document, the term set will be used for a collection of elements in the non-causal domain.
Series	In this document, the term series will be used for an ordered collection of elements in the non-causal domain.
List	In this document, the term list will be used for an ordered collection of elements in the causal domain.
Sequence	In this document, the term sequence is interchangeable with the term list but is generally restricted to discussions where the elements of lists are generated dynamically.

1.2. Galileo’s Paradox

More than 350 years ago, Galileo pondered the question of how to compare the lengths of two infinite sets, made famous in his infinite set mapping paradox [2]. Galileo questioned whether the set of natural numbers has more values than the set of the squares of natural numbers or whether the two sets are the same length. Figure 2 visualizes this paradox by showing there is a one-to-one mapping between every natural number and its square. Each natural number is paired with a square, as such, the set of squares should have the same length as the set of natural numbers. But paradoxically, the set of natural numbers has values that do not appear in the set of squares which

would imply their lengths are not the same. Galileo’s view of this paradox was that ideas of “greater”, “equal”, and “less” simply do not apply to infinite sets.

Figure 2: Galileo’s Infinite List Mapping Paradox for Natural Numbers and Their Squares

More than 200 years later, Cantor chose “equal lengths” as the founding principle of Cantorian Infinity. Like a two-sided coin, for the past 150 years, the “equal lengths” side has been studied, but the “different lengths” side has been relatively ignored. Interestingly, both solutions can be constructed in the causal domain of infinity.

1.3. The Causal Domain Setup

Let us describe a thought experiment that will be essential in constructing the two solutions to Galileo’s paradox and helping to determine how the non-causal to causal domain transformations work. Imagine a computer with data values stored in a computer’s finite memory. A user decides to insert a new data value into the memory at the first address and shift the other data values to the next higher address in memory. In this thought experiment, the computer memory will start at address 1, and the data stored at each address of interest will be equal to the address itself.

As with all computer algorithms, there exists a causal sequence of steps to transform and initial state into a final state. Figure 3 depicts this insert process. In step 1 data value 0 is in a temporary storage location ready to be shifted into the memory. A sequence of swap operations with temporary storage locations eventually results in all data elements being shifted to the next higher memory location.

Figure 3: Iterative Element Insert Process on a Finite Computer Memory

Now imagine a hypothetical computer system that can move all data values in the finite memory to the next location simultaneously (Figure 4). The result of the simultaneous move is indistinguishable from the result produced by the iterative process (Figure 3).

Figure 4: Simultaneous Element Insert Process on a Finite Computer Memory

Now extend the computer memory such that it is infinitely long (Figure 5). In the first scenario (iterative swapping) one piece of data will always be in temporary storage. Because there is no last memory location, the insert swap process will continue forever. The simultaneous insert, on the other hand, will complete in a single step. These two methods of looking at an infinite list insert are sufficient to construct both solutions to Galileo’s question in the causal domain.

Figure 5: Iterative and Simultaneous Element Insertion into Infinite Lists

Before proceeding, to be complete, let us consider the reverse of the insert process (Figure 6). This scenario remains the same as before except the data value previously inserted into the computer memory will be removed. All other data values then shift back to their original location. If the process is performed iteratively, an empty memory location will propagate along the memory forever as subsequent data values occupy emptied locations. Although data values are moving, this appears to an observer as if a ‘hole’ is propagating along the memory towards higher numbered memory addresses (shown using the dashed arrow). An iterative removal will never complete while a simultaneous removal completes in a single step.

Figure 6: Iterative and Simultaneous Element Removal from Infinite Lists

1.4. Conventions

The infinite list shift scenarios imply a specific concept of causality, that is, a sequence of steps performed in a specific order. In some cases, there is a single event which transforms a “before” state into an “after” state. Words like “simultaneously”, and “all at once” describe single-event causality. The number of steps can be finite or infinite depending on the situation. Words like “iteratively”, and “one at a time” are used to describe the transformation from the “before” state

into an “after” state using multiple steps. Even when not stated explicitly, the language used should make it clear whether a process is single-event causal or multi-event causal, and whether a process has a finite number of steps or an infinite number of steps.

Furthermore, the lengths of countably infinite lists will be expressed by the symbol ∞ . This paper is going to construct the answers to Galileo’s paradox. Since this paper needs to deal with lengths of infinite sets before the property of equal cardinality has been defined, ∞_n will refer to the number of elements in the set of natural numbers $[1,2,3, \dots, \infty)$, while ∞_w will refer to the number of elements in the set of whole numbers $[0,1,2, \dots, \infty)$.

2. Cantorian Infinity

2.1. Non-Causal Cantorian Infinity

In standard mathematics, no causal process is assumed. The ideas of list insert and removal operations (section 1.3) are not traditionally how sets are treated. Mathematics deals with relationships, not processes. A one-to-one mapping is simply a function, not a physical or temporal operation.

The core property of Cantorian Infinity, equal cardinality, is that if a one-to-one mapping exists between two sets, then the sets are the same size, regardless of whether the set size is finite or infinite. This property is simply set “by definition” and the remainder of the properties of Cantorian Infinity are derived from it.

2.2. Causal Cantorian Infinity

One of the useful things about the causal domain of Cantorian Infinity is that the properties of Cantorian Infinity can be constructed rather than being set “by definition”. In the end, the set of properties and their dependencies will be found to be in a circular self-consistent dependency structure. Because of this structure, the properties are essentially set “by definition”, but that is to maintain self-consistency, not because it is an arbitrary choice. The remainder of this section will be used to construct the properties of an infinite list insert operation under the causal Cantorian framework of infinity.

Because it is a circular dependency structure, one of the properties needs to be the starting point. It really doesn’t matter which one. I am going to start with the property of shiftability as a starting assumption and then work through the dependency structure showing that, by assuming a seamless shift, a seamless shift is possible.

2.3. The Initial Assumption

There are two possible solutions to the question posed regarding an insert on an infinite list (Figure 5). Consider the following two claims:

- Seamless Shift Claim: Every element can move because the location where it wants to move to has an element that itself can move; true for all infinite elements.
- Deadlock Claim: Every element cannot move because the location where it wants to move to itself cannot move; true for all infinite elements.

These are the only two possible values for the shiftability property of infinite lists. For Cantorian Infinity, assume a seamless shift is possible.

2.4. The Causal Steps of an Infinite List Insert

By assuming a seamless shift, a finite number of steps are required to perform an insert operation on an infinite list (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Finite Steps to Perform and Insert Operation on an Infinite List

There are multiple rows in Figure 7 with arrows connecting items. Each row represents a snapshot in time of the computer memory during the insert process. The arrows indicate movement of data values between steps to make it easier to track what has happened in a particular step. In the initial state there is a direct one-to-one correlation between each address and data value.

In step 1 the value to be inserted is moved into a temporary memory location. This can be thought of as part of the initial state, but breaking up a step into a finite number of sub-steps will result in the same answer. As such, I have decided to leave this as two individual steps.

Now, let us consider the implications of the assumption of a seamless shift. If a seamless shift is possible, all data values can be moved to the next memory address defined by the mapping function $f(x) = x+1$ where x is the current address and $f(x)$ is the new address (step 2). Data value '1' will move from address 1 to address 2, data value '2' from address 2 to address 3, and so on. Each data value in the memory, originally located at a unique address, is being reassigned to a new unique address via the given mapping function. All data values simultaneously move out of their current assigned memory location into a new location.

In step 3, the new data value '0' in the temporary memory location is then moved into empty address location 1, completing the insert process.

2.5. The Cardinality Property

The lengths of two infinite lists must be compared to resolve Galileo's question (section 1.1). But infinite list lengths are undefined, so a direct comparison is not possible. The infinite list insert process provides a mechanism to compare two undefined lengths. The utility of this lies in that it models both function mappings and list lengths in the same process. In the initial state there is a one-to-one mapping between one list of elements (addresses / natural numbers) and a second list of elements (data values / natural numbers). Both lists are identical (the mapping is the identify function $f(x) = x$) and so the number of addresses and data values must be the same. The process

starts with two lists that have undefined lengths, but it is known that they are the same length because they are copies of the same list.

There is then a process to insert an element into the second list which is completed in step 3. The final state is a one-to-one mapping between the source list elements (addresses / natural numbers) and the destination list elements (data values / whole numbers). Two different lists with the mapping $f(x) = x-1$. As a result of this process, the length of two infinite lists can now be compared relative to each other. Since the initial list length of addresses and data values are both \aleph_n , and since the resultant length of data values is \aleph_n+1 (a data value was inserted between the initial and final states) and since every address still has one and only one data value and all data values are in a memory location, then $\aleph_n = \aleph_n+1$, or rather, $\aleph_n = \aleph_w$. The two different infinite lists have the same length, or rather, they have equal cardinality.

The key point is not merely that the insert process completes, but that the causal process enforces a structural constraint: if a finite-event shift is possible, then the mapping between the initial and final state must preserve the number of elements. In a finite list, a seamless shift preserves cardinality because every element moves to a unique new location and no element is lost. This is then extended to the infinite case whereby if the shift completes in finitely many steps, then the mapping must preserve the number of elements. Thus the causal assumption forces the conclusion that $\aleph_n = \aleph_w$, rather than merely illustrating it.

Originally, the intent was to answer Galileo’s question about infinite list lengths. There is now a solution that can compare the list lengths of natural numbers and whole numbers. Unfortunately, this isn’t quite enough to answer Galileo’s question about the mapping to squares of numbers (Figure 2). But there are some things that are known that can help determine how to proceed. There are two ways to determine the number of destination elements for finite lists with one-to-one mappings. The first is to simply count the number of destination elements. But because there is a one-to-one mapping, the second way is to count the number of source elements. If there is a one-to-one mapping between two finite lists, then the list lengths are the same. Table 2 delineates when the source list length can be used to determine the destination list length.

Table 2: Destination List Length Can Be Determined From Source List Length

Mapping	Finite List	Infinite List
One-to-one	Yes	?
One-to-many	No	No
Many-to-one	No	No

The process of inserting an element into an infinite list (Figure 7) showed that this relationship between one-to-one mappings and list length also holds true for at least one set of infinite lists. The most reasonable extension to this knowledge is that, if a one-to-one mapping exists between two lists, then the list lengths are the same for all such lists. And as such, Galileo’s question is resolved, but it is partially resolved “by definition”. This section started with the assumption of a seamless shift. From that equal cardinality was shown for at least one infinite list. Then “by definition”, equal cardinality is extended to cover all infinite lists with a one-to-one mapping.

Updating Table 2 with this new information gives Table 3. The important thing to notice at this point is that the unknown value in Table 2 has been answered by extending the properties of a one-to-one mapping from the finite to the infinite. Because of this, equal cardinality is extended to all one-to-one mappings. Note that this is the founding principle of Non-Causal Cantorian Infinity.

Table 3: Destination List Length Can Be Determined From Source List Length

Mapping	Finite List	Infinite List
One-to-one	Yes	Yes
One-to-many	No	No
Many-to-one	No	No

2.6. The Causality Property

An assumption is made regarding causality to perform the insert process (Figure 7). An insert process acting upon an infinite list must act upon all elements of the infinite list in a finite number of steps. But why is it required that all the data values move in a finite number of steps? To see why, let us consider what it would mean to perform the same process using an infinite number of steps. For this, refer to the ideas from Figure 5 where an infinite list insert process is done iteratively.

There are no empty memory locations for the data value to move into when swapping one data value at a time. A data value at an address must first be moved to a temporary location before the previous data value in the temporary location can be moved to that address. There will always be one data value in a temporary location after each iteration of the while loop (Algorithm 1, Line 3).

Algorithm 1: A Sample Iterative Swap Process

```

1: # Iterative swap process
2: Address = 1
3: Temp[0] = 0
4: while True:
5:     Temp[1] = InfiniteList[Address]
6:     InfiniteList[Address] = Temp[0]
7:     Temp[0] = Temp[1]
8:     Address = Address + 1

```

This exercise can be extended to ask the question: instead of swapping data values one at a time, what if N data values were swapped at a time? In that case, N data values would be emptied into the temporary array. The temporary array now contains $N+1$ data values because the temporary array previously had one data value, leaving N empty memory locations. Then N data values from the temporary array could be moved into the empty memory locations. There would still be one data value in the temporary array at the end of each iteration of the swap process. In fact, the answer is that there must always be one data value in the temporary array regardless of the number of data values involved in a single step of the swap process. Taking the limit of the data values, N , involved in the swap process as N tends to infinity results in always one data value in the temporary array. Using a limit on a causal process is not normally done in mathematics. The mathematical mechanism that allows this will be described in section 4.

Figure 8: Graph of $f(\text{swap_num}, \text{swap_length})$

This particular limit is a limit of a sequence of limits (revisited in sections 4.3 and 5.3). The graph of this is shown in Figure 8. The limit is computed to determine the number of data values in the temporary array for each swap of the relocation process (swap_num axis). Then the limit of these limits is computed (thick solid line in the graph) as the number of data values in the swap process increases (swap_length axis). The surface described by these series of equations is a plane with function $f(\text{swap_num}, \text{swap_length}) = 1$.

Relocating data values using an infinite process requires the use of the limit to determine the state of the infinite list. If the limit had to be employed then the answer, 1 value in temporary storage (“Observation Point” in the graph of Figure 8), would not match the results in this section. By contradiction, a process with an infinite number of steps is not allowed. Therefore, an infinite list insert must be completed in a finite number of steps.

2.7. The State Mapping Property and Philosophy of Universals

Earlier it was mentioned that any step of the causal process could further be broken into a finite number of sub-steps. The reverse is also true where sub-steps can be combined. Let us look at the list insert problem as if it were done in a single step. Instead of having the arrows show the path the data values take, the arrows now show the connection between the memory locations from the initial to final states (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Initial to Final State Mapping

In the initial state, there is an infinite list of ordered pairs which are described by the mapping function $f(x) = x$. In the final state, after the insert, there is an infinite list of ordered pairs which are described by the mapping function $f(x) = x-1$.

To show equal cardinality, all infinite ordered pairs in the initial state and final state must pre-exist as real abstract objects as well as the connection between them (arrows between the ordered pairs in the initial and final state). In other words, everything must be reified (sections 2.9 and 3.9

for more information). In the causal model, the mapping arrows cannot be treated as optional interpretive devices. They must exist as concrete components of the state because the causal process refers to them: the causal process cannot be described as a state transition. Therefore, equal cardinality in the causal domain requires the existence of all ordered pairs as completed objects. This is precisely the philosophical stance of reification.

Here is where the causal domain provides an insight that is not possible when strictly viewing Cantorian Infinity in the non-causal domain. In standard mathematics, sets can be real abstract objects, but the mapping functions are not considered as such. But here we see that even the mappings must be reified.

2.8. Other Starting Points

As mentioned previously, a seamless shift was arbitrarily chosen as the starting point. But any of the properties could have been chosen as an alternate starting point. For example, equal cardinality could have been assumed. Let us briefly take a look at equal cardinality as the starting point.

Suppose step 2 in Figure 7 is decomposed into two sub-steps. In the first sub-step (2.a), all elements move into a temporary buffer, and in the second sub-step (2.b), all elements move from the buffer into their new location. In sub-step 2.a, the buffer contains ∞_n elements. In sub-step 2.b, the memory must accept ∞_n elements into $\infty_n - 1$ available locations (all locations except address 1). For this to succeed, the system must treat ∞_n and $\infty_n - 1$ as interchangeable. This is yet another hidden circular dependency. The process that proves that $\infty_n = \infty_n + 1$ already assumes $\infty_n = \infty_n - 1$.

2.9. Summary of the Properties of Cantorian Infinity

Table 4: Properties and Values of Causal Cantorian Infinity

Property	Value
Cardinality	Lists with a one-to-one mapping have equal lengths.
Philosophy of Universals	Mathematical objects are real abstract objects that pre-exist.
Causality	Insertion and removal processes on infinite lists must occur with a finite number of steps.
Shift Behavior	An insert or removal operation on infinite lists behaves seamlessly.
State Mapping Property	The state mapping between ordered pairs in the initial and final states are real abstract objects.

The properties above form a circular dependency structure which can be visualized as shown in Figure 10 (Causal Cantorian Infinity). The shiftability property and state mapping property are left out of the larger oval because they are specific properties of infinite list insert operations, whereas the other three are generic to infinity in general. Grouping them this way is only done as a means of organization. All properties are in a self-consistent dependency structure. If any single property is changed, self-consistency is broken.

Figure 10: Property Structure of Causal Cantorian and Inverse Cantorian Infinity

Traditionally, mathematics deals with process-less relationships. The non-causal domain property structure is within the smaller dashed oval in the figures. This simply eliminates the properties that exist only in the causal domain leaving the circular dependency between cardinality and the philosophy of universals. In the causal domain, a state is defined by a complete list of ordered pairs (address, value). In the non-causal domain, a set is defined by the same ordered pairs, but without temporal interpretation. The equivalence follows because every causal state can be ‘frozen’ into a non-causal description, and every non-causal description can be interpreted as a causal state with zero steps. The only requirement for this equivalence is that the ordered pairs exist as completed objects — which is exactly the reification assumption. Thus finite-event causality plus reification yields a structure identical to the non-causal Cantorian universe.

It is not obvious that equal cardinality and reification are in a circular dependency structure in Non-Causal Cantorian Infinity. But it can now be seen that equal cardinality can only be true if all elements of sets and the mappings between them are real abstract objects that pre-exist. And if all elements of sets and the mappings between them are real abstract objects that pre-exist, then the two sets must have equal cardinality. And because the elements and mappings are real abstract objects, non-causal mathematics is equivalent to finite-event causal processes.

Causal Cantorian Infinity is self-consistent when the properties in Table 4 are selected as shown. Changing any one property will break that self-consistency. The question I will pursue next is what happens when all properties are changed. Does the alternate set of properties shown in Figure 10 (Causal Inverse Cantorian Infinity) result in a self-consistent framework of infinity?

One final note, it is very likely that the reader will have already recognized the process of inserting an element into an infinite list as a reframing of the Hilbert Hotel analogy [3]. Interestingly, the Hilbert Hotel analogy uses causal processes such as insert, removal, and interleave to perform manipulations on infinite lists to demonstrate different aspects of non-causal Cantorian Infinity. The reason Hilbert’s analogy is so successful is that operating in the causal domain is equivalent to the process-less math of Cantorian Infinity.

3. The Inverse Framework of Infinity

3.1. The Properties of the Causal Inverse Framework

Cantorian Infinity and the inverse framework of infinity have different causal interpretations of infinity. The Cantorian Infinity interpretation of the universe is probably best described as static, that is, a set can be thought of as pre-existing in full, real. The inverse framework's view of the universe is dynamic, a process that is unfolding without end, generated. One analogy is to imagine a video zooming into a fractal. Because of the nature of fractals, no two frames of the video are the same. The Cantorian Infinity's static interpretation of this video is that every frame pre-exists. For the inverse framework, the frames of the video are being generated dynamically. Note that an observer watching the video cannot determine which option is the source of the video they are watching.

The framework of infinity being developed here is completely foreign to the accepted framework of infinity because of relative cardinality, and as such, may initially be non-intuitive. Irrespective of intuition, what is being done here is simply to show that this inverse framework is self-consistent.

3.2. The Initial Assumption

As with Causal Cantorian Infinity, the properties of the inverse framework will also be constructed first in the causal domain. Let us assume that an insert operation on an infinite list cannot happen because the list is in deadlock. Because the list is in deadlock, the finite sequence of steps shown in Figure 7 will not work. The computer memory with an iterative insert process (Figure 5) is the appropriate process for this exploration.

3.3. The Causality Property

Unlike causal Cantorian Infinity, which requires finite-event causality for insert processes, the inverse framework will require infinite list operations to be performed with infinite-event causality. That is, the process needs to be broken into an infinite number of causal steps. Because the process is infinite, the limit will need to be used to determine the result of the operation. The definitive answer to the behavior of a causal process as it tends to infinity will be the limit of the causal process. As mentioned previously, mathematics does not generally use the limit with processes. In section 4 the mechanism to convert the algorithms of the causal domain into a non-causal mathematical operation will be shown.

Using the limit of a causal process is not completely new to math. One such example is Zeno's Dichotomy Paradox [4] where a person follows the infinite process of traveling half the distance to a destination in a given time, and then half the remaining distance in half the time, and so on. The classical mathematical solution to this paradox is to reframe this as a converging series and use the limit to show that the result using an infinite sequence of steps is the same as if the person had traveled the distance in a single step (I will revisit this in section 4.1).

3.4. Generators

As a reminder, two undefined lengths need to be compared using an infinite number of steps. I will do two things in this section. The first will be to set up a mechanism to compare the two undefined list lengths of the natural numbers and whole numbers algorithmically. The second will be to show how the properties of the inverse framework can be seen in infinite algorithmic processes.

Some basic algorithmic building blocks are needed to get an intuitive understanding of the inverse framework. The first building block is the generator method. For this, a concept is borrowed from the Python programming language. The generator method has a ‘yield’ operator which returns a value and then pauses the method until the next time the method is called.

Algorithm 2: Generic Sequence Generator

```

1: # Generator to produce an infinite list of numbers
2: def sequence_gen( start_val, incr_val ):
3:     element = start_val
4:     while True:
5:         yield ( element )
6:         element += incr_val

```

Algorithm 2 will produce natural numbers if the start_val is 1 and incr_val is 1. After the yield statement on line 5 is executed, the method is paused (execution flow is returned to the calling program). The next time this method is called, execution will start on the line after the yield statement (line 6). Algorithm 3 is an example program that calls the “sequence_gen” method to produce the natural numbers.

Algorithm 3: Observing the Natural Numbers

```

1: # Sample calling program
2: def main:
3:     # Create a pointer to the natural_numbers_generator method
4:     naturals = sequence_gen( start_val=1, incr_val=1 )
5:
6:     # Loop forever
7:     while True:
8:         # Get the next number from the generator
9:         num = next( naturals )
10:        print num

```

Observed output:

1
2
3
...

The while loop in Algorithm 3 line 7 will never end. Each time through the while loop the next natural number will be generated and printed. This code will produce the infinite sequence of natural numbers.

3.5. Observers and Processes

I find that, for myself, visual diagrams are much more understandable than code, which is required for preciseness. The algorithmic code can quickly become complicated and loses its ability to clearly illustrate a point. As I work through this section, I will frequently switch between discussing an algorithm and a visualization of the algorithm. Figure 11 is a visualization of the loops in the code of Algorithm 3 being unrolled. The observer in the diagram is equivalent to the print statement in the code selection on line 10.

Figure 11: Visualization of a Generator and Observer of the Natural Numbers

Note that the code selection has a fixed relationship between the generator and the observer. This is only to make the code easier to write. Critically, the generator needs to be thought of as an independent process from the observer process. An observer can independently move up or down the sequence of numbers created by the generator, the only thing it can't do is pass the generator.

This algorithmic interpretation is not restricted to a single process per sequence. Multiple processes can act on the same sequence and processes can catch up with one another, but they cannot pass each other without repercussions. Processes acting on the sequence are like steps in a recipe: in some cases, changing the recipe order will produce a different result. Order of operation of the processes must be maintained just like order of operation principles in math. I find it helpful to mentally envision these processes as an animation of moving machines (which is why they are drawn with caterpillar tracks). Unfortunately, this dynamic mental view does not translate well into the fixed figures drawn in this paper, so some imagination is required.

3.6. Mathematical Methods

To compare two infinite list lengths, an infinite algorithm is needed to perform an insert operation in a similar fashion to the process used in causal Cantorian Infinity. Let us create the function mapping $f(x) = x-1$ using the sequence generator that was previously defined. This function mapping generator (which internally uses the natural number generator and whole number generator) returns pairs of numbers (Algorithm 4 and visualization in Figure 12).

Algorithm 4: $f(x) = x - 1$ Using Dual Generators

```
1: # Generic mapping function taking to generators as inputs and returning pairs of numbers
2: def mapper_generator( srcList_gen, dstList_gen ):
3:     while True:
4:         n = next( srcList_gen )
5:         f_n = next( dstList_gen )
6:         yield ( n, f_n )
7:
8: # Sample calling program
9: def main:
10:    naturals = sequence_gen( start_val=1, incr_val=1 )
11:    wholes = sequence_gen( start_val=0, incr_val=1 )
12:    pair_list_gen = mapper_generator( srcListGen=naturals, dstList_gen=wholes )
13:    while True:
14:        pair = next( pair_list_gen )
15:        print pair
```

Observed output:

```
1 0
2 1
3 2
...
```


Figure 12: Visualization of $f(x) = x-1$ Using Dual Generators

Notice that an observer cannot differentiate whether they are witnessing paired numbers created by number generators or witnessing the mappings of two infinite lists with all numbers pre-existing. A mapping function can also be viewed as a process that converts an input number into an output number (Figure 13, Algorithm 5 and a visualization in Figure 14).

Figure 13: Visualization of a Mapping Function

Algorithm 5: $f(x) = x - 1$ Using a Mapping Function

```

1: # Natural to whole number mapping generator using single generator and function
2: def func_n_minus_x_generator( input_list, x ):
3:     while True:
4:         # Get the next number from the sequence
5:         n = next( input_list )
6:
7:         # Perform the mapping
8:         f_n = n - x
9:
10:        # Return the mapped pair
11:        yield ( n, f_n )
12:
13: # Sample calling program
14: def main:
15:     # Create a pointer to the mapping generator, natural number generator is the input.
16:     pair_list = func_n_minus_x_generator( sequence_gen(start_val=1, incr_val=1), x=1)
17:     while True:
18:         pair = next( pair_list )
19:         print pair

```

Observed output:

```

1 0
2 1
3 2
4 3
...

```


Figure 14: Visualization of $f(x) = x-1$ Using a Single Generator with Mapping Function

To reiterate, crucially, there is no discernable difference to an observer process between any of the different notions of a mapping function. This is true whether all mappings pre-exist simultaneously, mappings are created from dual generators, or the mappings are being created by a function acting on the outputs of a single generator. An observer on the source sequence will simply see that every element has a mapping.

3.7. Infinite List Insert Operations

Now with the basic building blocks established, let us use them to perform an insert operation on an infinite list (recreating the graph of Figure 8). Because the different views of how a mapping exists are indistinguishable to an observer process, let us proceed with just one of these views when performing the example for an insert. Let us begin with the mapping function $f(x) = x$ (Algorithm 6, line 60. Figure 15, mapping process) because it starts with two identical lists. There will be a single source sequence and a process operating on it that creates the mapping such that each source element is mapped to the destination element with the same value. Note that this is how the causal derivation for Cantorian Infinity started, a relative comparison between the lengths of two lists could be made because the initial two lists were identical.

Next, an insert process is required, implemented as another generator (batch insert generator, defined on line 15, called on line 65). The insert method will use a temporary storage location to perform the swap process used to shift the list.

How to take the limit of an algorithm still needs to be defined. The limit of an algorithm is no different than a normal mathematical limit. To determine the limit, the state of the algorithm is checked to see if it is diverging or converging, and if converging, to what value (this conceptual explanation will be formalized in section 4.3). In section 2.6 it was shown that two limits were involved. The first was the behavior as the swapping process tended to infinity (that is the limit of the swap number as the swap number approached infinity). The second was the behavior of the swap process as the number of elements involved in the swap process tended to infinity. The insert algorithm has an iteration count (swap_num). In addition, the algorithm has another input that indicates the number of elements to shift each time through the infinite loop (swap_length).

Algorithm 6: Complete Insert Algorithm

```

1: # Using a mapped_list generator and a swap_length length, return batches of mapped pairs
2: def batch_pair_generator( swap_length, mapped_list ):
3:     while True:
4:         # Clear the contents of the batch list
5:         batch = []

```

```

6:
7:     # Collect 'swap_length' items from the mapping generator
8:     for _ in range( swap_length ):
9:         batch.append( mapped_list )
10:
11:     # Return the collected pairs
12:     yield batch
13:
14: # Perform an insert of length swap_length each iteration
15: def batch_insert_generator( length_delta, ins_val, swap_length, mapped_list ):
16:     batched_mappings = batch_pair_generator( swap_length, mapped_list )
17:
18:     # Get the first set of pairs from the underlying generator
19:     first_pair_batch = next( batched_mappings )
20:
21:     # Split the batched pair list into a source and destination temporary lists
22:     src_temp_list[]
23:     dst_temp_list[]
24:     for new_src_val, new_dst_val in first_pair_batch:
25:         src_temp_list.append( new_src_val )
26:         dst_temp_list.append( new_dst_val )
27:
28:     # Yield the first item from source list and the inserted value
29:     swap_num = 1
30:     src_val = src_temp_list.pop(0)
31:     # Item popped from first list but not second list
32:     length_delta += 1
33:     yield ( swap_num, length_delta, src_val, ins_val )
34:
35:     # Now continue returning pairs
36:     while True:
37:         # while the source list still has items
38:         while src_temp_list:
39:             # Item popped from first list but not second list
40:             src_val = src_temp_list.pop(0)
41:             length_delta += 1
42:
43:             # Item popped from second list but not first list
44:             dst_val = dst_temp_list.pop(0)
45:             length_delta -= 1
46:
47:             yield ( swap_num, length_delta, src_val, dst_val )
48:
49:             # replenish the lists since source list is empty
50:             pair_batch = next( batched_mappings )
51:             for new_src_val, new_dst_val in first_pair_batch:
52:                 src_temp_list.append( new_src_val )
53:                 dst_temp_list.append( new_dst_val )
54:             swap_num += 1
55:
56: # Sample calling program
57: def main:
58:     # Pointer to the input generator starting with natural number identity function f(x)=x
59:     naturals = sequence_gen( start_val=1, incr_val=1 )
60:     identity_gen = func_n_minus_x_generator( input_list=naturals, x=0 )
61:     ins_val = 0
62:     swap_length = 1 # Rerun program and change swap count
63:     init_delta = 0 # Initial delta between x and f(x) is 0 by definition
64:     # Set up the batch insert mechanism to insert a value into the input mapped pairs
65:     output_mapping = batch_insert_generator(init_delta, ins_val, swap_length, identity_gen)
66:
67:     while True:
68:         mapping_info = next( output_mapping )
69:         print ( mapping_info )

```

Observed output with $swap_length=1$ and $ins_val=0$ (shown in bold to easily identify). The first column is the iteration count, the second column in italics is the length delta, and the next two numbers are the mapping pair:

```

1 1 1 0
2 1 2 1
3 1 3 2
4 1 4 3
...

```

Observed output with $swap_length=3$ and $ins_val=0$:

```

1 1 1 0
1 1 2 1
1 1 3 2
2 1 4 3
...

```


Figure 15: Visualization of an Insert Process

3.8. The Cardinality Property

Because deadlock was assumed, infinite causality was required to perform the insert (section 3.3). The causality property imposes the restriction that the limit of the infinite process on an infinite list is the definitive result. What can be seen is that the state and output of the algorithm converges. Solve for the limit of $length_delta = f(swap_num, swap_length)$ as $swap_length$ and $swap_num$ tends to infinity. The function $f(swap_num, swap_length) = 1$ for all values of $swap_length$ and $swap_num$ and, as such, the limit of the $length_delta$ is 1 (observation point on Figure 8).

From the perspective of an observer following the insert process, the list of whole numbers has one more element than the list of natural numbers, or rather, $\infty_w = \infty_n + 1$. Note that this conclusion differs radically from Cantorian Infinity which claims that $\infty_w = \infty_n$. Under the inverse property constraints, different infinite lists can have different lengths. The length of the list is undefined, but relative length comparisons between list lengths can be made.

This only solves Galileo's question for the relationship between the list lengths of the natural numbers and whole numbers in a similar fashion to what was observed for Cantorian Infinity. But since there is one example of an infinite list where list lengths are not equal, the reasonable solution is to extend it for all infinite lists. Table 5 shows an updated version of Table 3 for the inverse framework. Notice that in the inverse framework, the value selected extends the behavior of infinite lists, not the behavior of one-to-one mappings as this was the most reasonable extension based on the available information. Because the list lengths are not equal, as a direct result, the length of the source list cannot be used to determine the length of the destination list.

Table 5: Destination List Length Can Be Determined From Source List Length

Mapping	Finite List	Infinite List
---------	-------------	---------------

One-to-one	Yes	No
One-to-many	No	No
Many-to-one	No	No

And as such, Galileo’s question is resolved, but it is partially resolved “by definition”. This section started with the assumption of a deadlock. From that relative cardinality was shown for at least one infinite list. Then “by definition”, relative cardinality is extended to cover all infinite lists. The inverse framework answers Galileo’s question differently than Cantorian Infinity. It claims that the length of the list of natural numbers is different than the length of the list of squares of natural numbers. This is not surprising given that the properties of the inverse framework are inverses of the properties of Cantorian Infinity.

3.9. The State Mapping Property and Philosophy of Universals

Let’s take a closer look now at the state mapping property. Unlike Causal Cantorian Infinity which has an initial and final state, the causal inverse framework has an initial state, an infinite number of subsequent states, and no final state. In each state there is no consistent mapping between the ordered pairs of the initial state and the current state. Figure 16 is the infinite version of the Figure 9. The elements that the observer has seen have the mapping $f(x) = x - 1$. These are the ordered pairs with bold outlines in the figure. If the mappings pre-exist, then the light-shaded ordered pairs after the observer continue to have the mapping $f(x) = x$. If the ordered pairs after the observer are being generated, the light-shaded ordered pairs do not exist yet. What is important is that the observer sees the correct mapping produced by an insert operation. The state mappings are relative to the observer. As such, state mappings adhere to a nominalist view of the Philosophy of Universals.

Figure 16: State Transitions of the Infinite Causal Insert

In the causal inverse framework, we can take this one step further. The function mappings themselves must also be treated in a nominalist fashion. To explain this, I will borrow a concept from object-oriented programming. In object-oriented programming, an object (like an element in the list of natural numbers) is not a passive container, but rather knows how to operate on its own data. The core principle of object-oriented programming is that the behavior lives with the data that

it acts on. As an example, the function mapping $f(x) = x-1$ is a behavior that is associated with the source domain object. The mapping behavior can be applied to the source domain object's data value without having any real connection between a source and destination object. The inverse framework's mapping philosophy is that a function mapping is not a real object, but rather it is an abstract property of the source domain only. The fact that there is a mapping does not provide any information about the length of the destination list.

As expected, Cantorian Infinity and the inverse framework have opposite implications. In Cantorian Infinity, the state mappings and function mappings are real abstract objects. In the inverse framework, state mappings and function mappings are not real objects, everything is relative to an observer.

3.10. The Shift Property

What does it mean then to perform an insert operation on an infinite list and the limit of the number of items in temporary storage is always 1? The observed behavior is a contradiction. An insert on an infinite list should have nothing in temporary storage when it has completed. And since there is always something in temporary storage, then the conclusion is that, by contradiction, an infinite list insert operation could not happen. It follows that the list must have been in deadlock. This is consistent with the initial assumption.

Philosophically, in the inverse framework it is not possible to insert an element into an infinite list in a single step. The insert operation must be performed as a process with an infinite number of steps. Causal Cantorian Infinity has a very understandable relationship between the causal and non-causal domains. This is because the ideas of a fixed relationship between the initial and final states can map directly to the idea of a fixed non-causal relationship. And since it has the property of equal cardinality, it is easy to imagine making a unique connection between every natural number and every whole number. On the other hand, the inverse framework has the property that the length of the natural numbers and whole numbers is different, so a direct mapping in a single step is not possible in the causal domain. But it is possible to map every element in the non-causal domain because there are always more numbers to choose from (infinity has no end).

3.11. Circular Dependencies

The inverse framework assumed that an infinite shift was not possible. Because an infinite shift is not possible, the problem must be broken into an infinite number of steps (otherwise it could have been completed as a single step). Once broken into an infinite number of steps, the results show that the list is in deadlock and an infinite shift is not possible.

Unpacking this a bit more: if the shift cannot occur in finitely many steps, then the only remaining option is an infinite-event process. But an infinite-event process requires that each element eventually moves. In the deadlock scenario, no element can move because each depends on another that also cannot move. Thus infinite-event causality implies deadlock. Conversely, if deadlock is assumed, then no finite-event process can succeed, and the only possible causal interpretation is an infinite-event one. The two properties therefore mutually enforce each other, forming a circular dependency analogous to the Cantorian case. Just as in the framework of Cantorian Infinity, the most that can be done is to show that the set of properties are self-consistent.

3.12. Self-Consistency

What I set out to show was that the inverse framework was self-consistent and a true inverse of the properties of Causal Cantorian Infinity. There is no requirement that it matches any intuitive understanding that one might have. The inverse framework of infinity is a fully self-consistent framework mutually exclusive to Cantorian Infinity. Effectively, these two sets of self-consistent properties describe a binary model with two stable solutions.

Let us extend the information previously listed in Table 4. Table 6 details what is currently known about the similarities and differences between the two frameworks. It was shown that by changing just one property of the set of properties of Cantorian Infinity, and then following the logic to its conclusion, that the remaining properties naturally resolved to their “inverse” values. It is not so much that changing one property breaks the self-consistency of Cantorian Infinity. Rather, changing one property forces the remaining properties to invert themselves to maintain self-consistency.

Table 6: Causal Property Comparison Between Cantorian Infinity and the Inverse Framework

Property	Cantorian Infinity	Inverse Framework
Cardinality	Absolute lengths of infinite lists are undefined, but lists with one-to-one mappings have equal lengths.	Absolute lengths of infinite lists are undefined, but relative length comparisons can be made. Insertion and removal processes on infinite lists change the list length by the number of elements inserted or removed.
Philosophy of Universals	Mathematical objects are real abstract objects that pre-exist.	Mathematical objects are not real abstract objects that pre-exist, but rather can be thought of as generated dynamically.
Causality	Insertion and removal processes on infinite lists must be performed with a finite number of steps.	Insertion and removal processes on infinite lists must be performed using an infinite number of steps. The limit of the infinite number of steps is the definitive result.
Shift Behavior	An insert or removal operation on infinite lists behaves seamlessly.	An infinite list is in deadlock. Insert or removal operations on infinite lists cannot happen.
State Mapping Property	The state mapping between ordered pairs in the initial and final states are real abstract objects. A function mapping is as real as the source and domain element.	The state mapping between ordered pairs are not real abstract objects but are rather properties that are relative to an observer. A function mapping is a property of the source domain element only.

An insert process on an infinite list is like playing musical chairs, but instead of removing chairs, the insert “game” adds players. In Causal Cantorian Infinity, if all players get up and shift simultaneously, every player including the new player will find a chair to sit in. In the inverse

framework, if all players try to move simultaneously, there is a deadlock situation where no player can move, and as such, the players must perform an iterative swap process. Every player has an original seat, and every player will eventually have a final seat. In both universes, the resultant behavior is required to maintain self-consistency, and the resultant behaviors follow from the constraints of the properties that define that universe.

4. The Mathematical Generator Tool

4.1. Zeno's Dichotomy Paradox

Previously it was mentioned that the causal infinite processes of the inverse framework and the underlying non-causal mathematics are interchangeable. Until now I have been intuitively using generators, algorithms, and limits of algorithms in the causal domain. These intuitive uses all stem from a single deeper mathematical principle. Let us revisit Zeno's Dichotomy Paradox to show this principle. Zeno's Dichotomy paradox is shown causally in Figure 17 with each subsequent step highlighted. There is no final step in this process.

Figure 17: Traditional Steps of Zeno's Dichotomy Paradox

There are ways to think about this problem being broken into an infinite number of steps (Figure 18). Let us think of travelling the distance as a set of experiments. The person walks a different number of sub-steps depending on the experiment. In the first experiment, the person walks the entire distance from start to finish as a single operation. The full path is split into two halves in experiment 2. In experiment 3 the last interval is split into two halves, and so on, forever. All experiments yield the same result.

Figure 18: Steps of the Infinite Cut Sequence Generator for Zeno's Dichotomy Paradox

This is effectively an algorithm that breaks up the path walked using an infinite process. Each experiment has an increasing quantity of sub-paths. The sum of the individual paths, for every experiment, is always equal to the full path, regardless of the number of sub-paths. Results are shown in (Table 7). This may seem trivial, but the limit of this non-causal infinite process as the number of experiments tends to infinity matches the expectation.

Table 7: State of the Cutting Algorithm

Experiment	Number of Pieces	Distance Travelled
1	1	1
2	2	1
3	3	1
4	4	1
...

The original working of the paradox (Figure 17) can also be written as a similar non-causal algorithm. Instead of thinking of the steps the person takes, treat them as individual experiments (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Zeno's Dichotomy Paradox as a Collection of Experiments

The limit of the result of an infinite number of experiments (Table 8) converges towards the time it takes to travel the distance in a single step.

Table 8: State of the Converging Algorithm

Experiment	Number of Pieces	Distance Travelled
1	1	1/2
2	2	3/4
3	3	7/8
4	4	15/16
...

4.2. The Non-Causality/Causality Transformation Generator

The answer to the sequence of experiments in Figure 19 is the same as the answer in Figure 17. They are interchangeable. A transformation generator is mathematical tool that converts a causal sequence into an infinite collection of finite experiments (Table 9). A translation generator is needed because infinite-event causality cannot be represented by a single infinite process. Instead, we approximate the infinite process by a family of finite experiments, each representing a partial execution. The generator collects all such finite approximations. The limit over the generator corresponds to the ‘completed’ infinite-event process. This construction mirrors how analysis treats infinite sequences: the infinite object is defined as the limit of all finite prefixes. The generator therefore provides the mathematical bridge between causal infinite processes and non-causal infinite structures

Table 9: Definition of Generator, Limit of a Generator, and Convergence of a Limit of a Generator

Tool	Description
Generator	<p>A transformation generator is an <i>unordered</i> infinite collection of finite experiments.</p> <p>Examples given experiment number N:</p> <p>Zeno’s Dichotomy Paradox (exact): The exact path broken into N pieces Zeno’s Dichotomy Paradox (converging): A converging path with N pieces Natural numbers: A finite list of the first N natural numbers Insert on infinite list with infinite steps: An insert on a finite list of length N Algorithm: The state of the algorithm after N iterations of the algorithm The digits of $1/\phi$: The first N terms of partial sums (section 6.4) Integration: The number of slices N subdividing a shape (section 6.5) The Hilbert space-filling curve: The order N of the curve (section 6.6)</p>
Limit of Generator	<p>The limit of the generator is the definitive answer for determining the result for a problem. The limit of the generator is the value as the number of <i>ordered</i> experiments tends to infinity.</p>

The translation generator gives us the mathematical tool to perform a translation between the algorithmic causal and mathematical non-causal domains of the inverse framework. It converts an infinitely causal process into an infinite collection of finite experiments. Whether an insert operation on an infinite list or the generation of a fractal, the translation generator provides the capability to take the limit of a causal process. Note that this is no different than the traditional method of taking the limit of a converging series of partial sums. It just extends that property of math to cover causal processes.

4.3. Equivalence of a Causal List Insert and Non-Causal Limit

In the introduction it was claimed that the inverse framework of infinity more closely aligns with the algorithms of computer science. This is because the concept of a generator aligns perfectly with the concept of iterative loops found in programming languages. Each iteration of a loop in the algorithm can be considered a different experiment. For example, the first experiment is the result after one pass of the algorithm. The Nth experiment is the result after N passes of the algorithm.

All prior inverse framework processes in this paper (infinite list insert as an unending swap process, algorithmic programs, visualizations with generator machines) are fully interchangeable with the concept of the translation generator defined here. Consider the visualization of the sequence of natural numbers and its generator in Figure 11. The diagram is a visual unrolling of an algorithm. Each element in the visual chain refers to an experiment where the length of the list of natural numbers contains N elements for that experiment. Table 10 shows the first four experiments of this infinite collection of experiments.

Table 10: Output of the Natural Number Generator

Experiment	Natural Number Generator Output
1	[1]
2	[1, 2]
3	[1, 2, 3]
4	[1, 2, 3, 4]
...	...

Let us return full circle to an insert operation. Algorithm 6, Figure 15, and Table 11 are completely interchangeable. Mathematically, the generator object creates an infinite collection of finite experiments. This infinite collection can be defined by a function that has two inputs, swap_num and swap_length (thick table borders). The output is the relative length delta (last column). This table summarizes the entire graph of Figure 8. For each input pair an arbitrary experiment number is assigned (see section 5.3). Each experiment has a finite input list containing the first swap_num*swap_length elements of the natural numbers. There is a generated output list showing the result of the insert operation. The next column shows the element from the destination list that got moved into temporary storage, and finally the relative length delta. An insert on a finite list always has a value in temporary storage, and the relative length delta between the source and destination list is always 1.

Table 11: Experiments of an Infinite List Insert (Inserting Element with Value = 0)

swap num	swap length	Experiment number	Input List	Output List	Element in Temporary Storage	Relative Length Delta
1	1	1	[1]	[0]	1	1
2	1	2	[1, 2]	[0, 1]	2	1
3	1	3	[1, 2, 3]	[0, 1, 2]	3	1
4	1	4	[1, 2, 3, 4]	[0, 1, 2, 3]	4	1
1	2	5	[1, 2]	[0, 1]	2	1
2	2	6	[1, 2, 3, 4]	[0, 1, 2, 3]	4	1
3	2	7	[1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6]	[0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5]	6	1
...

The inverse framework determines the result based on the limit of the experiments of the translation generator. In this case, the limit of the relative length delta, as the experiment number tends to infinity, is equal to 1. Since these different interpretations (algorithm, visualization,

mathematical generator) of an infinitely causal process are interchangeable, it is acceptable to switch back and forth between them.

4.4. Bidirectionality

The translation generator can take a causal process and convert it into an infinite collection of finite experiments. But the reverse is also true. An infinite collection of finite experiments can be converted into a causal process. For example, the photon in Feynman's path integral formulation [5]. Feynman's showed that to compute the probability amplitude for a photon to travel from A to B, one must sum the phase contributions from every possible path the photon could have taken between points A and B. This statement describes a mathematical generator. Feynman's path integral is an infinite collection of finite experiments (each experiment is one path that the photon can take). Note that here a sum is taken instead of a limit.

Because of bidirectionality, this infinite sum can be converted into a causal process where the photon does test every possible path, continually summing the phase of each subsequent path. The algorithm to choose the next path for the photon to test could be a random Monte Carlo style simulation or could use the Causal Axiom of Choice (section 5.4).

5. Solving Problems in Both Universes – Compatible Results

The only example seen so far, an infinite list insert, had incompatible results regarding the relative number of elements between two infinite lists and whether a list insert was in deadlock or not. A single example is not sufficient to develop a comprehensive understanding of the inverse framework. This section contains a set of problems where Causal Cantorian Infinity and the causal inverse framework are compatible with each other and with non-causal mathematics.

5.1. Repeating Fractions

Let us examine a case where, historically, both causal frameworks have been used interchangeably. When taught to math students in primary school, the causal inverse framework is used (although it is not thought of in those terms), and when taught to more advanced math students, Causal Cantorian Infinity is used. Let us look at the fraction $1/3$ which, when written as a decimal number, is $0.333\dots$ repeating forever. This can be represented by the infinite series as in Figure 20.

$$\frac{1}{3} = \frac{3}{10} + \frac{3}{100} + \frac{3}{1000} + \dots$$

Figure 20: Series of Partial Sums to Calculate 0.333... is Equal to 1/3

But instead of solving it as a limit of a series of partial sums, I will show the solution by showcasing the concepts in this paper of shifting infinite lists. Causal Cantorian Infinity can show that the repeating decimal representation is equal to the fraction (Figure 21).

$$\begin{array}{r}
 \text{let } x = 0.33333\dots \\
 \text{then } 10x = 3.33333\dots \\
 \text{subtract both sides:} \\
 \begin{array}{r}
 10x = 3.33333\dots \\
 - x = -0.33333\dots \\
 \hline
 9x = 3.00000\dots
 \end{array}
 \end{array}$$

therefore $x = 1 / 3$

Figure 21: Showing $0.333\dots = 1/3$ Using Cantorian Infinity

This uses a seamless removal operation (shift-out) to effectively multiply by 10. After the shift there is still a one-to-one mapping between every digit in both numbers. If this were the list process used earlier for a shift-in operation, the memory locations are the place locations (tenths, hundredths, etc.), and the data values are the decimal values (always 3). Shifting one value out of the computer memory (moving the 3 from the tenth's location into the one's location) means there is still an infinite number of digits. Each fractional digit has a paired digit in both the minuend and the subtrahend after the shift has completed. And since all digits are paired, and each digit's difference is 0, all infinite result fractional digits must be 0.

I should probably qualify my statement about primary school math students. They do not generally solve the problem of calculating the fraction from the repeating decimal representation. Rather, they calculate the reverse, showing the repeating decimal representation from the fraction. This is done by employing a divide which requires an infinite number of sub-steps (Figure 22). The student would identify that the result for each sub-step has the same inputs and same outputs (converges), therefore the result will always be 3's, forever.

$$\begin{array}{r}
 0.33333\dots \\
 3 \overline{) 1.00000\dots} \\
 \underline{- 9} \\
 10 \\
 \dots
 \end{array}$$

Figure 22: Showing $1/3 = 0.3333\dots$ Using an Iterative Approach

To go in the reverse in the causal inverse framework, let us set up an algorithm to perform the shift operation in Figure 21 with an infinite number of steps. Algorithm 7 shows the inverse framework's solution by creating an algorithm that performs the operation $(10*\text{num}) - \text{num}$ by substituting $10*\text{num}$ with a shift. Each of the infinite number of sub-steps acts on a single digit in the minuend and subtrahend.

Algorithm 7: Solving $0.333\dots = 1/3$ Using the Inverse Framework of Infinity

```

1: # A generator to generate 0.3333... The first value returned is the 10ths decimal place
2: def zero_point_three_repeating_generator():
3:     while True:
4:         yield ( 3 )
5:

```

```

6: # Perform the shift and subtract to effectively model (10*num) - num.
7: def ten_x_minus_x_gen( fraction_digit_list ):
8:     # Get the first pair from the underlying generator.
9:     first_digit = next( fraction_digit_list )
10:    # This returns the value in the 1s location (10*num - 0)
11:    yield ( first_digit )
12:
13:    # Now continue shifting and subtracting (returning the fraction locations)
14:    previous_digit = first_digit
15:    borrow = 0
16:    while True:
17:        current_digit = next( fraction_digit_list )
18:        sub_result = current_digit - previous_digit - borrow
19:        borrow = 0
20:        if sub_result < 0:
21:            sub_result += 10
22:            borrow = 1
23:
24:        yield ( sub_result )
25:        previous_digit = current_digit
26:
27: # Sample calling program
28: def main:
29:     result_digit_gen = ten_x_minus_x_gen( zero_point_three_repeating_generator )
30:
31:     iteration_count = 0
32:     while True:
33:         iteration_count += 1
34:         result_digit = next( result_digit_gen )
35:         print ( iteration_count result_digit )

```

Observed output:

```

1 3
2 0
3 0
4 0
...

```

The results after each additional iteration of the main while loop can be considered as an independent experiment. Now let's take the limit of this algorithm. In the observed output, the iteration count is the experiment number. The algorithm first prints the ones digit location value of the result, then the tenths digit location value, then one hundredths digit location value and so on. Take the limit as the iteration count tends to infinity to find the value of the n^{th} decimal digit. The limit is clearly 0 because the function that models the output is $f(x) = 0$. Therefore, $10*x - x = 3.0$ and $3.0/9 = 1/3$.

Note that the above algorithm is a simplification. Once the algorithms get too complicated, they tend to be less useful in illustrating the behaviors being described in this paper. The above algorithm is missing two things. First, it only works for single digit repeating patterns. Second, the above algorithm does not have the second variable to alter the number of digits that are processed per iteration. The limit of the sequence of limits as both the iteration count and the digit length approach infinity is what needs to be calculated. But it should be obvious that the result will be the same regardless of the number of tokens processed per iteration. Adding this extra detail would have only cluttered the algorithm so it was left out.

What is shown here is that both causal Cantorian Infinity and the causal inverse framework produce compatible results and they are the results that match non-causal mathematics.

5.2. Reproducing Cantor's Mapping of Natural Numbers to All Integers

Cantor showed there is a mapping from the natural numbers to all integers. This can be shown in Causal Cantorian Infinity using the Hilbert Hotel analogy in a clever way by creatively interleaving the positive and negative integers (not shown here, the method is widely available online). To recreate this with the inverse framework, start with a generator producing the list of all integers. It requires two generators to produce a sequence of integers that is unbounded on both ends (Figure 23). An observer process can operate on the sequence independently from the generators and there is no reason to limit generators to act on only one end of the sequence.

Figure 23: Dual Generators Producing All Integers

Recall these are just algorithms and the algorithms can be modified or rearranged to create a desired scenario. Separate the sequence into two halves and connect them as in the visualization of the algorithm in Figure 24. The top generator is producing the natural numbers (source elements). The bottom two generators came from Figure 23 and are producing all integers (arbitrarily picking one of them to produce zero). To do this, an interleaver method is introduced in Algorithm 8.

Algorithm 8: Mapping the Natural Numbers to the Integers

```
1: # Generic interleaver. Takes two generators as inputs. The first number returned
2: # will be from listA and the second from listB. This will then repeat forever.
3: def interleaver_generator( listA_gen, listB_gen ):
4:     while True:
5:         numA = next( listA_gen )
6:         yield ( numA )
7:         numB = next( listB_gen )
8:         yield ( numB )
9:
10:
11: # Sample calling program
12: def main:
13:     # Generator [0, -1, -2, -3, ...]
14:     zero_and_neg_gen = sequence_gen( start_val=0, incr_val=-1 )
15:
16:     # Generator [1, 2, 3, ...]
17:     one_and_pos_gen = sequence_gen( start_val=1, incr_val=1 )
18:
19:     # Generator the natural numbers as the source list in the mapping
20:     srcList_gen = sequence_gen( start_val=1, incr_val=1 )
21:
22:     # Interleaver to create [0, 1, -1, 2, -2, 3, ...]
23:     dstList_gen = interleaver_generator( zero_and_neg_gen, one_and_pos_gen )
24:
25:     # Generate mapped pairs between natural numbers and all integers
26:     mapper_gen = mapper_generator( srcList_gen, dstList_gen )
27:
28:     while True:
29:         mapped_pair = next( mapper_gen )
30:         print ( mapped_pair )
```

Observed output:

1 0
 2 1
 3 -1
 4 2
 5 -2
 6 3
 ...

Figure 24: Visualization of an Algorithm for Mapping Naturals to Integers

Relative cardinality means that the lengths of two infinite lists can be compared relative to each. To find the relative length comparison between natural numbers and integers, the algorithm needs to be changed to create a situation where a relative comparison can take place. Figure 25 visually shows the desired algorithm. This algorithm is similar to the algorithm used to show that the whole numbers had one more value than the natural numbers. It starts with a replicator to create three identical lists. These lists are effectively the identify function, and as such, their lengths are equal. In combination with the other processes in the diagram, the length of the list of natural numbers can be related to the length of the list of integers (the insert is required because the replicator cannot produce the integer value of 0).

Figure 25: Process to Determine Relative List Length Between Naturals and Integers

I will not write out the algorithm for the above equation because the algorithm requires that the processes that operate on the list be independent from each other whereas, in the algorithms so far, the processes have been in lock step. But, if this were coded as an algorithm, the result would be $\text{length_delta} = f(\text{swap_num}, \text{swap_length}) = 2 * \text{swap_num} + 1$. The limit of the sequence of limits for this function as both swap_num and swap_length approach infinity is infinity. Therefore, the list of integers has infinitely more numbers than the natural numbers (as expected).

As the swap_num tends to infinity, the asymptotic line that best fits the limit is $f(\text{swap_num}, \text{swap_length}) = 2 * \text{swap_num} + 1$ (not just asymptotic, it is exactly this equation). This equation is true for all values of the swap length. The integers have infinitely more values than the natural

numbers, but more specifically, the relative relationship is that there are twice as many (plus one) values as the natural numbers.

5.3. Reproducing Hilbert's Mapping of Natural Numbers to An Infinite List of Infinite Lists

Cantorian Infinity can show that the natural numbers can be mapped to an infinite set of infinite sets. This can be done in the causal domain using the Hilbert Hotel analogy (again, visualizations are available online). The non-causal domain manages this using a clever method of interleaving infinite lists as shown in Figure 26. In essence, the natural numbers in the infinite set of infinite sets can be mapped to a continuous line drawn through all infinite sets and all elements of each set such that the line covers every element of every set once and only once. Each element can then be uniquely assigned to a natural number.

Figure 26: Interleaving an Infinite Number of Infinite Lists

Let us reproduce this result with the causal inverse framework using the algorithmic tools already developed. One such way to demonstrate a similar mapping is to swap out the current interleaver method with a recursive interleaver method (Algorithm 9, Figure 27).

Algorithm 9: Mapping the Natural Numbers to an Infinite List of Infinite Lists

```

1: # Recursive interleaver with initial list passed in as an input
2: def recursive_interleaver_generator( listGen ):
3:     # The first list is the input list
4:     listA = listGen
5:
6:     # The second list is a recursively interleaved list of an infinite number of lists
7:     listB = recursive_interleaver_generator( listGen )
8:
9:     # Alternate between listA and listB
10:    while True:
11:        numA = next( listA )
12:        yield ( numA )
13:        numB = next( listB )
14:        yield ( numB )
15:
16: # Sample calling program
17: def main:
18:     # The whole numbers (this will be infinitely replicated with the recursive interleaver)
19:     wholes_gen = sequence_gen( start_val=0, incr_val=1 )
20:
21:     # The natural numbers, the source domain
22:     naturals = sequence_gen( start_val=1, incr_val=1 )
23:
24:     # The destination domain, and infinite number of lists interleaved
25:     dstList_gen = recursive_interleaver_generator( wholes_gen )
26:
27:     # The generic mapping between the source and destination list
28:     mapper_gen = mapper_generator( srcList_gen=naturals, dstList_gen )
```

```

29:
30:   while True:
31:       mapped_pair = next( mapper_gen )
32:       print ( mapped_pair )

```

Observed output:

```

1 0 ← from list 1
2 0 ← from list 2
3 1 ← from list 1
4 0 ← from list 3
5 2 ← from list 1
6 1 ← from list 2
...

```


Figure 27: Simplified Mapping Diagram Showing a Mapping to an Infinite List of Infinite Lists

Note that this particular recursive algorithm does not produce the same path through the elements of the infinite sets as done in Figure 26, but it does produce a continuous path through all infinite lists and all elements of each infinite list. An algorithm can be easily constructed for the path shown in Figure 26, however, the visualization of that algorithm is complicated. Algorithm 9 just happens to have an easier visualization to draw which is why it was picked for this example.

Refer to section 4.3 where Table 11 showed the results of the multi-variable function $f(\text{swap_num}, \text{swap_length})$ for the translation generator. This function can be converted to a single variable function $f(\text{experiment_num})$ by using the concept in this section. To do that, the generators connected to the interleavers are simply replaced with the output of the full algorithm producing the relative length delta output for a different unique swap_length .

5.4. The Generator as the Causal Axiom of Choice

As seen in the algorithms in this paper, generators and other processes can be combined into more complex generators. For example, the complex recursive process in Algorithm 9 and Figure 27 can be simplified such that a single destination generator creates the numbers of the combined complex process (list generation and recursive interleaving combined) (Figure 28).

Figure 28: Mappings to Infinite Lists of Infinite Lists Shown as a Combined Process

In so doing, the generator device will now be recognized for what it is: the Causal Axiom of Choice. The Causal Axiom of Choice is a finite experiment generator that can create a sequence of finite experiments without specifying the order of the experiments. Unlike the generators seen so far which produce specific ordered sequence of numbers, the Causal Axiom of Choice generator produces numbers where all that is necessary is to know that an order exists.

Figure 29: The Generator as the Axiom of Choice

In Con-Causal Cantorian Infinity, the combination of the properties of Cantorian Infinity and the Axiom of Choice result in the ZFC framework of infinity. There is a difference between the Axiom of Choice in the two frameworks. In Cantorian Infinity, the numbers pre-exist. In the inverse framework, there is no requirement that the numbers pre-exist, just that an order exists.

In section 4.3, Table 11, the transformation generator was used to create an *unordered* infinite set of finite experiments for an insert operation. The concepts in section 5.3 can be used to convert the multi-dimensional function with inputs *swam_num* and *swap_length* into a single-dimensional function with input *experiment_num*. The causal axiom of choice can then be used to order the experiments by the length of the input list and to filter out duplicates.

6. Solving Problems in Both Universes – Incompatible Results

Cantorian Infinity and the inverse framework are compatible with each other in certain situations, with some examples as seen in section 5. In this section I will go through several additional examples showing how the two frameworks are incompatible. This incompatibility is traditionally interpreted as paradoxes. But now these paradoxes will be seen for what they are, different results from two different incompatible mathematical universes.

6.1. Operation Reversibility and Process Annihilation

The behaviors of infinite insert and removal operations described by Causal Cantorian Infinity are not reversible without storing external information. This is true because the final list length is the same regardless of the number of elements inserted or removed. The information about the operations performed has been lost. On the other hand, the behaviors of infinite lists described by the causal inverse framework are reversible without external information. The necessary

information is embedded in the processes that are operating on the list. Viewing an insert operation with the arrow of time pointing forward is indistinguishable from a reversal of an insert operation with the arrow of time pointing in the reverse direction. At any point during an insert process, the sequence of events can be reversed and the processes on the list will return the list to its initial state.

In a similar light, inverse processes on an infinite list will cancel each other out (an insert followed by a removal). Let us take an infinite list and perform an insert operation using an insert method where a data value is stored in a temporary location. Once the insert process has started, a removal operation with its “hole” can also be started, following behind the insert process. The removal process can catch up to, but not pass, the insert process (order of operations being preserved). But processes can be combined if they are operating on the same element (assuming the order of operation on the same element is also preserved). Because the two processes are doing the opposite operation on the same element, the two processes can be combined into a single process which will cancel with each other resulting in the “hole” being filled with the data value in the temporary storage location and both processes ceasing to exist. As such, an insert followed by the opposite process of a removal returns the array back to its initial state. In fact, because the processes themselves have ceased to exist, the initial and final states of the list are identical. Note that the idea of processes catching up to each other relies on the ability of processes to operate independently of each other (the moving machines of the loop unrolling visualizations).

6.2. The Banach-Tarski Paradox

I have chosen a specific sub-step of the Banach-Tarski Paradox [6] to discuss decomposition paradoxes. For this example, let us start with an infinite collection of points that are part of a circle (Figure 30, left image).

Figure 30: A Collection of All Points from a Circle, Assigned to the Whole Numbers

Let us assign numbers to the points in the collection. The top point of the circle is number 0, which is missing, then a fixed distance N separates all subsequent points clockwise around the circle. Point 1 is N units away from point 0, and so on, to create points 2, 3, etc. This is an infinite collection of non-overlapping points $[1, 2, \dots, \infty)$, that is, the list of natural numbers.

According to Causal Cantorian Infinity, it is possible to replace the missing point. To replace the missing point, simply apply the mapping function $f(x) = x-1$ to all remaining points, as in the list

insert processes, and then move all the points simultaneously to their new location (Figure 30, middle image). Point 1 will move into the empty hole where point 0 used to be, point 2 into point 1's old location, and so on. Because the list of points around the circle is infinite and unique, shifting them counterclockwise simultaneously fills in the missing points and all other points will remain filled. Along with additional steps, Banach and Tarski show that starting with the collection of points that make up a sphere, the sphere can be completely duplicated, effectively creating something from nothing (or more precisely, creating something from everything and having everything remaining).

Under the causal inverse framework this step is not possible because the list of points around the circle is in deadlock. However, if the points were to be moved iteratively (Figure 30, right image), the sequence of moves looks like the removal process shown in Figure 6 in the computer memory analogy. Point 1 will move to point 0 leaving an empty hole at location 1. Point 2 will move into the hole at location 1 moving the hole to location 2, and so on. An observer following that process will see that all locations of the circle are filled by an element. The hole found after the removal process is there, it will just never be visible to the observer. The missing point is never fully removed.

All decomposition paradoxes that result from the behavior of infinite lists are essentially the same in the causal domain. They rely on the ability to insert something or remove something without affecting the length of an infinite list. This is true whether it is the Banach-Tarski paradox, a dictionary style paradox, or any other decomposition paradox (as is seen in section 6.5 for real numbers).

In Non-Causal Cantorian Infinity, equal cardinality and reification show that, if a one-to-one mapping exists between all points of a source sphere to a destination sphere, then the two objects have equal volume. In the non-causal inverse framework, even if there is a one-to-one mapping, the elements of the source domain provide no information about the elements in the destination domain because mappings are properties of the source domain only.

6.3. Cantor's Diagonalization Proof

Cantor's Diagonalization Proof [7] relies on the properties of Cantorian Infinity to prove that the real numbers are uncountable, and as such, there exist hierarchies of infinity. This proof is well known, so I won't reproduce the details. But it is important to show that it depends on all three properties of Causal Cantorian Infinity.

It relies on equal cardinality to construct a one-to-one relationship between each unique real fraction between 0.0 and 1.0 to a unique decimal digit (the diagonal digits). It relies on reification because all digits must exist in the array. And the process must be done in a finite number of steps (if done causally).

Let us look at this problem in the causal inverse framework. First, let us create the real numbers between 0.0 and 1.0 using an infinite number of experiments. Let us group experiments by the number of digits in the finite value. Each group of experiments will contain all unique encodings for the given number of digits. This is shown in Figure 31 for the first four groups. Note that this entire process can be thought of as the output of a complex generator algorithm. In group 1, the array is a 1x2 grid. In group 4, it has grown to a 4x16 grid because the three additional digits has increased the number of possible unique encodings from 2 to 16.

Figure 31: First Four Steps of the Inverse Framework

An observer following a unique branching path from the start, forever, will be observing a unique real number being generated. Let us number each experiment (numbered arrows in Figure 31). The total cumulative number of experiments, N , for each group, S , is calculated using the formula $N = 2^{S+1} - 2$. For each value S , the generator needs N^2 more natural numbers to map the new experiments. There is no group S of the generated sequence that runs out of natural numbers to map the new experiments at that step. This is true even as the group number N tends to infinity. Finally, a single line can be constructed (see Figure 26) that weaves through every experiment, therefore, a mapping exists from the natural numbers to every real number. Real numbers are countable in the inverse framework.

6.4. Convergence

Let us look at converging sequences and series of partial sums. The value for $1/\phi$ can be calculated via a sum of a converging infinite series. The partial sums of that series give better and better approximations of $1/\phi$ as additional partial sums are added to the result (Table 12).

Table 12: First 5 Terms of Converging Sequence of an Analytic Series for $1/\phi$

N	Term	Sum of First N Terms Converging Towards $1/\phi$
1	1/2	0.500000000...
2	1/8	0.625000000...
3	-1/128	0.617187500...
4	1/1024	0.618164063...
5	-5/32768	0.618011475...
...	...	0.618033988...

In the causal inverse framework, the generator and processes creating the series will continue forever. There are two observers here. The first type of observer is observing the value of the sum for a given experiment. An observer watching the steps of the series will never see the converging sum equal to the exact value of $1/\phi$. In the table above, N is equivalent to the experiment number

and the sum column is the result. The limit of N , as N tends to infinity, shows that the result converges towards $1/\phi$.

There is a second observer which is observing the digits of the series being generated. It is important to distinguish between the two observers. This observer is different than the observer of an infinite sequence (Figure 11) where the exact value of each element in the sequence is known (for example, the natural numbers). An observer watching the digits of a converging series only makes a step forward when the digit it moves to next in the converging series of partial sums is stable. From now on, I will specifically call an observer with such a property as a “stable” observer to distinguish it from an observer that has no restrictions on its movement which will simply be called an observer. As the stable observer traverses the generated series, it will see that all digits in the converging value and the actual value are identical. However, even though the stable observer sees that they are identical, the two values are not required to be equal for the inverse framework to be self-consistent. In the inverse framework there is no last step. A limit of a series does converge towards a value, but the converging series is never equal to that value. A stable observer cannot differentiate between the two values.

There is then the question of applicability to Cantorian Infinity. If this process requires an infinite number of finite experiments, then it is equivalent in the causal domain to a process with an infinite number of steps. Cantorian Infinity requires finite-event causality. From this, it can be seen that the limit theorem is a property of the inverse framework and is not applicable to Cantorian Infinity. If Cantorian Infinity were to attempt to calculate this result, it must use something similar to what was seen in section 5.1 where the series of partial sums in Figure 20 was calculated using a finite number of steps.

6.5. Cavalieri’s Widthless Lines Paradox

Let us look at the concept of Cavalieri’s Widthless Lines [8]. Cavalieri imagines a shape composed of an infinite number of widthless lines, such that, when rearranging the lines, the total area of the shape remains constant (Figure 32, shapes 1-3). Cavalieri’s Widthless Lines produces the correct result when rearranging lines such that the new shape has the same width as the old shape.

Figure 32: Three Shapes Comprised of the Same Widthless Lines Rearranged

This is not true when the new shape has a different width than the original shape. Since there are an infinite number of lines, and just like in the list insert processes in this document, every line can be moved to a new location chosen by the output of a formula, move the lines in shape 1 to a new location using the formula $f(x) = 2x$ (shape 4).

Every line in Shape 4 will have a one-to-one mapping with a line in Shape 1. Since there is a one-to-one mapping, equal cardinality and reification, Cantorian Infinity shows the two shapes have the same number of lines. The properties of Causal Cantorian Infinity allow the lines to shift to their new location with no holes left behind. Because the second shape was created only from lines from shape 1 (and all the lines from shape 1), the two shapes must have the same area.

Critically, in Cantorian Infinity all finite shapes have the same area, that is, area is scale-invariant. This can be shown by simply scaling a starting shape to a new shape with the new desired dimensions and then dissecting the new shape and rearranging the pieces into the final shape. Dissecting a shape into sub-pieces does not change the area. Scaling the newly created sub-pieces does not change the area as was seen above. Given that many finite shapes can be shown to have the same area with this method, it can be extended so that all finite shapes then must have the same area. There is a paradox between this result and the result from Calculus using integration. To understand why, let us investigate how the causal inverse framework works in this situation.

The lines cannot be moved in the inverse framework because they are in deadlock. But what if they were moved using an infinite number of sub-steps? Each line that is moved will leave behind a hole. That hole will then be filled in by another line that is moving leaving another hole, and so on. To an observer of the line moving process, the total number of lines has not changed. This means the area of the new shape will be equal to the area of the original shape (matching what Cavalieri predicted with his Widthless Lines). However, the new shape from an infinite shift process is not the same as Shape 4 because the new shape has an infinite number of holes propagating forever as the transformation unfolds whereas Shape 4 is solid, without any holes. In the inverse framework, moving the lines maintains the area just as Cavalieri predicted. Note that an observer following the process will not see the holes.

Mathematics traditionally solves the area problem by using integrals to calculate the area of shapes. An integral uses the limit theorem to calculate the area by summing an infinite number of rectangles with a delta width, as the delta width of each rectangle tends to zero. Let us look at how integrals use the properties of the inverse framework. Instead of thinking about Riemann sums as the limit as the width of slices tends to zero, think about an infinite collection of finite experiments with the limit as the number of experiments tends to infinity (Figure 33). This figure shows one such example where the number of slices in experiment N is 2^{N-1} .

Figure 33: Steps of the Infinite Slice Sequence Generator for Integration

If this example were written as an algorithm, then each step of the algorithm cuts each existing slice in half and alters the height of one of the halves. At each step along the way, the state of the algorithm can be observed to see if it is converging (Table 13).

Table 13: State of the Integral Algorithm

Experiment	Number of Slices	Width of Slices	List of Slices	Total Area of Slices
1	1	1	[2]	$2/1 = 2.0$
2	2	$1/2$	[2, 1]	$3/2 = 1.5$
3	4	$1/4$	[2, $3/4$, 1, $1/2$]	$5/4 = 1.25$
4	8	$1/8$	[2, $7/8$, $3/4$, $5/8$, 1, $3/8$, $1/2$, $1/8$]	$9/8 = 1.125$
...

The inverse framework states that if a problem is subdivided into an infinite collection of experiments, then the limit as the number of experiments tends to infinity is the definitive answer to the problem. With Riemann sums, as the experiment number tends to infinity, the number of slices tends to infinity. And as the number of slices tends to infinity, the area of the Riemann sum tends to the area of the surface it is subdividing. Like in section 6.4, there are two observers. One is observing the sum of the array of slices being generated. The other is a stable observer following the sequence of converging digits of the sum of the array of slices.

It should come as no surprise that integration, which uses the limit, is a property of the inverse framework as just shown in section 6.4. The appropriate way to determine area in Cantorian Infinity is via the method using Cavalier's Widthless Lines. From this, scale-invariance can be shown to be a property of other dimensional objects as well. A finite line can be scaled, preserving its length. A finite cube can be scaled, preserving its volume. This confirms what was seen earlier with the Banach-Tarski paradox which shows that the volume of a sphere is preserved when a one-to-one mapping is found between a single sphere and another sphere. In Cantorian Infinity, geometric measures are scale-invariant. The property of equal cardinality applies to all dimensions.

Let us also address the situation where Cavalier's Widthless lines is compatible in both frameworks. Both Cantorian Infinity and the inverse framework are compatible when rearranging the lines to form a new shape (Figure 32, shape 1-3). This is because the result of rearranging elements in a list (swapping) produces the same result whether the list can seamlessly shift or is in deadlock. On the other hand, attempting to scale a shape by moving the lines results in a mismatch because scaling is, in effect, a shift operation, which is affected by deadlock.

6.6. The Hilbert Space-Filling Curve Paradox

In Cantorian Infinity, the concept of space filling can be described as a continuous surjection of a 1-dimensional set onto a 2-dimensional region. The Hilbert Space-Filling curve is a mathematical example which is commonly used to show how this might occur. Let us look at the Hilbert Space-Filling Curve [9]. The Hilbert Space-Filling Curve is a limit of piecewise linear curves as shown for the first three orders in Figure 34:

Figure 34: First Three Orders of the Hilbert Curve Using a Single Tile Shape

From what we have already seen, this example is not applicable in Cantorian Infinity because it relies on an infinite number of steps (or experiments, as each order number can be considered a finite experiment) whereas operations in Cantorian Infinity must be completed in a finite number of steps.

In the inverse framework, the limit of the infinite collection of finite experiments is the definitive result. The tiles become smaller as the order of sequences of curves increases, and as a result, constructed line will cover the square with more and more detail. The ratio of points covered by the curve to the total points of the unit square is always 0 for every value N of the order of the curve. Taking the limit as the order tends to infinity shows that the ratio tends to 0. Likewise, the line in Inverse Cantorian Infinity will never become infinitely intersecting because there is no last order.

The Hilbert Space-Filling Curve is not traditionally thought of as a paradox. This is an interesting case where the method of using the Hilbert Space-Filling Curve is the correct way to solve the problem in the inverse framework and is not actually applicable to Cantorian Infinity. In the inverse framework, the Hilbert Space-Filling Curve is not space-filling.

6.7. Dealing with Ordinals

The concept of ordinals captures the idea of “first, second, third, etc.”. Ordinals are more about the position in a sequence, rather than the quantity of elements in a sequence (length of the list). Unlike regular numbers, In Cantorian Infinity ordinals can count beyond infinity. One simple way to envision this is shown using the process in Figure 35. Imagine the infinite list of natural numbers in a queue (initial state), waiting to access a resource. Using Causal Cantorian Infinity, the first element can be shifted out of the queue (into a temporary storage location), and the rest of the list will seamlessly shift to their new locations. The length of the queue is unchanged due to equal cardinality. Now move the first element from its temporary storage to the back of the queue. The first item, now at the back of the queue, has infinity + 1 items before it. After the first set of infinite ordinals (1, 2, 3, etc.) a new number is reached, traditionally denoted $\omega + 1$.

Figure 35: Ordinals in Causal Cantorian Infinity

How then would this look under the properties of the inverse framework? In the inverse framework shifting an element out means that there is one less item in the remainder of the queue. And by that reasoning, moving the removed element to the back of the queue adds one element back in, not changing the length of the total number of elements in the queue. In this scenario, the concept of counting past infinity ($\omega + 1$) is not required.

Using an infinite number of steps is the appropriate way to move the item to the back of the queue in the inverse framework. The solution is to perform an infinite number of swap operations as shown in Figure 36. In the first step, elements 1 and 2 are swapped. In the second step, 2 and 3 are swapped, and so on. Conceptually, the first person in line is walking to the back of the queue via an infinite process of swap operations.

Figure 36: Ordinals in the Inverse Framework Undergoing a Swap Process

Figure 37: Visualization of the Algorithm of the Ordinal Swap Process

Let us consider the observer in Figure 37. The observer will be able to see all natural numbers except the element moving backwards in the queue. Said another way, there is no natural number that the observer won't see, except number 1, as the observer follows its forever long process of inspecting the queue. It is known that item 1 is still in the queue, just ahead of the observer somewhere. As far as the observer is concerned, every element in the queue is ahead of element 1 which is effectively at the end of the queue without requiring the need to count past infinity.

There is more than one observer in this process. The swap process itself is an observer. Both the original observer and the swap process see that all elements of the queue have a predecessor and a successor. Contrast this to Cantorian Infinity which adds the additional qualification that the first ordinal after infinity has no predecessor. That is, in Cantorian Infinity there is always a connection to the next successor ordinal, but sometimes there is no connection to an actual predecessor

ordinal. In the inverse framework, all ordinals always have a successor and a predecessor. The inverse framework does not have ordinals after infinity.

6.8. The Photon Analogy of an Infinite List Insert

To conclude, I am going to add one last analogy that I find helpful. This is a real-world analogy for the process of inserting an element into an infinite list and an observer not being able to catch up to it. Think of a photon that is injected (inserted) into the universe. When the photon is inserted, it will travel away from the insertion point at the speed of light (or speed of causality). An observer can be placed anywhere along the path of the photon and will observe the photon when it reaches the observer. This is equivalent to having a finite list with an insert operation. But if there is no observer along the path, then the photon will continue to travel forever, without end, like an infinite list insert. Imagine an observer that then sets out from the original insert point, following the photon. The observer will never be able to reach the photon, but the observer still knows that the photon is there, somewhere ahead of itself.

7. Formal Axiomatic Definitions

This section contains formal axiomatic definitions of the Inverse Cantorian framework of infinity.

7.1. Axiom N_1 – Relative Cardinality

For any two infinite sets A and B, the existence of a one-to-one mapping $f:A \rightarrow B$ does not entail that $|A|=|B|$. Instead, a one-to-one mapping determines a relative comparison of sizes:

- If there exists an injective $f:A \rightarrow B$, then A is no larger than B
- If there exists an injective $g:B \rightarrow A$, then B is no larger than A
- If both injections exist, the sets may still differ in size, relative cardinality is not symmetric.

Interpretation:

Cardinality is order-like, not equality-like. A bijection does not collapse distinctions between infinite magnitudes.

7.2. Axiom N_2 – Nominalism (Anti-Reification of Mappings)

Mappings between infinite sets are not abstract objects that exist independently of the processes that generate them [10].

A mapping is:

- a rule or procedure,
- not a completed totality,
- and not an entity that can be invoked to justify size equivalence.

Consequences:

- No appeal to “completed bijections” as objects.
- No inference from the existence of a mapping to the identity of set sizes.
- Infinity structures are understood procedurally, not as reified Platonic objects.

7.3. Axiom N₃ – Infinite-Event Causality

Any process that transforms one infinite list into another, including those corresponding to injective or bijective mappings, requires infinitely many causal steps. No infinite transformation can be completed in a finite number of events [11], [12].

Formally:

If a mapping $f:A \rightarrow B$ acts on infinitely many elements, then the induced process has order type ω ; it cannot terminate in finitely many steps.

Consequences:

- No “simultaneous” or “single-event” infinite shifts.
- No finite-event completion of bijections.
- Infinite processes never yield a final, completed state that can be used to infer cardinality equality.

7.4. Axiom N₄ – Non-Collapse of Infinite Magnitudes

If a process inserts or removes a single element from an infinite list, the resulting list has a different cardinality from the original.

Formally:

if A is infinite and $B = A \cup \{x\}$ or $B = A \setminus \{x\}$, then $|A| \neq |B|$.

Interpretation:

This axiom is the inverse of Cantor’s “ $|A| = |A \cup \{x\}|$ ” principle. It ensures that infinite sizes behave monotonically, not independently.

7.5. Axiom N₅ – Process-Dependence of Size Comparisons

The relative size of two infinite sets is determined only by the causal structure of the processes that map one into the other.

Formally:

For infinite sets A and B , the comparison $|A| < |B|$, $|A| > |B|$, or $|A| \sim |B|$ is defined by:

- the existence of an injective process from one into the other,
- the absence of an injective process in the reverse direction,
- and the impossibility of collapsing these relations into equality.

The axiom ensures that cardinality is procedural, not structural.

7.6. Relating the Inverse Cantorian Axioms to Cantorian Axioms

This paper argues that Cantorian Infinity rests on equal cardinality, reification, and finite-event causality. The inverse framework replaces each with its negation:

Table 14: Formal Comparison Between Cantorian and Inverse Cantorian Infinity

Cantorian Properties [13]	Inverse Cantorian Properties
---------------------------	------------------------------

Equal cardinality from bijection	Relative cardinality (N_1)
Reification of mappings	Nominalism (N_2)
Finite-event completion of infinite processes	Infinite-event causality (N_3)

Axioms N_4 and N_5 are natural consequences that make the system mathematically usable.

8. Conclusion

Over 350 years ago, Galileo started a sequence of exploration into infinite lists. This eventually led to the Cantorian framework of infinity which has been explored by generations of mathematicians. In this paper, I showed that Causal Cantorian Infinity and the causal inverse framework are self-consistent and mutually exclusive. I also showed that the causal version of each framework is equivalent to its non-causal version. From this, we identified how to determine if a mathematical theorem belongs to Cantorian Infinity or the inverse framework. Specifically, whether it employs finite-event or infinite-event causality when dealing with infinite sets.

Constraining a set of properties in two mutually exclusive ways is like choosing a universe to live in. Both universes can be explored to see their behaviors, but they exist independently of each other. Proofs in one universe remain valid in that universe but do not apply to the other universe and proofs that straddle both universes are not legal. Neither universe is inherently wrong so long as the property set is consistent with both itself and the rest of math in that universe. The only way to select between these different universes is to choose one to be the accepted universe “by definition”. For the case of Cantorian Infinity and the inverse framework, the example problems suggest that the inverse framework is the correct model for physical reality and should therefore be the primary universe.

The inverse framework aligns with physical reality because physical processes never complete infinite operations in finite time. Every physical shift, propagation, or causal chain proceeds through sequential events. This matches the infinite-event causality assumption. Likewise, physical theories do not require the existence of completed infinite sets; they only require rules for generating arbitrarily large finite structures. This corresponds to nominalism rather than reification. Thus, the inverse framework mirrors the operational structure of physical processes more closely than the Cantorian one. Furthermore, following Cantorian Infinity to its conclusion results in equal cardinality for all geometric measures which, likewise, does not match with physical reality.

I believe that axiom N_1 , relative cardinality, is the best candidate for a fundamental axiom to choose between the two universes. This axiom alone forces the remaining axioms, and directly negates Cantor’s foundational axiom.

9. References

- [1]: Quine, W. V. O. “New Foundations for Mathematical Logic.” *American Mathematical Monthly* 44, no. 2 (1937): 70–80.
- [2]: Galileo Galilei. *Dialogues Concerning Two New Sciences*. Translated by Henry Crew and Alfonso de Salvio. Dover Publications, 1954. (Originally published 1638.)

- [3]: Hilbert, D.: *Über das Unendliche*. *Mathematische Annalen*. 95, 161–190 (1926)
- [4]: Aristotle: *Physics*. Book VI, Chapter 9. Clarendon Press, Oxford (1984)
- [5]: Richard P. Feynman (1948). “Space–Time Approach to Non-Relativistic Quantum Mechanics.” *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 20(2), 367–387.
- [6]: Banach, S. & Tarski, A.: *Sur la décomposition des ensembles de points en parties respectivement congruentes*. *Fundamenta Mathematicae*. 6, 244–277 (1924)
- [7]: Cantor, G. (1891). *Über eine elementare Frage der Mannigfaltigkeitslehre*. *Jahresbericht der Deutschen Mathematiker-Vereinigung*, 1, 75–78.
- [8]: Andersen, K.: *Cavalieri’s Method of Indivisibles*. *Archive for History of Exact Sciences*. 31, 291–367 (1985)
- [9]: Hilbert, D. (1891). *Über die stetige Abbildung einer Linie auf ein Flächenstück*. *Mathematische Annalen*, 38, 459–460.
- [10]: Field, H. *Science Without Numbers: A Defence of Nominalism*. Princeton University Press, 1980.
- [11]: Thomson, J. F. “Tasks and Supertasks.” *Analysis* 15, no. 1 (1954): 1–13.
- [12]: Benacerraf, P. “Tasks, Super-Tasks, and the Modern Eleatics.” *Journal of Philosophy* 59, no. 24 (1962): 765–784.
- [13]: Cantor, G. *Contributions to the Founding of the Theory of Transfinite Numbers*. Dover Publications, 1955. (Original work published 1895–1897.)

Acknowledgements

I’m deeply grateful to my children for their thoughtful help in proofreading the early drafts of this work and for their unfiltered honesty about my writing. Their feedback reshaped nearly every section; this is the sixth full rewrite of a topic that seems to stretch on without end (multiple puns intended). From refining the analogies to reordering how ideas unfold, their insights made this document far clearer and more approachable. I also want to thank my wife for her unwavering support. Having someone who genuinely believes in you makes an enormous difference. This project has been a long, demanding journey, and her patience throughout has meant the world to me.